

A.—THE SĀHASA MALLA INSCRIPTION ON THE UPRIGHT SLAB
NORTH OF THE HÆTA-DĀ-GE, FOUND WHILST CUTTING THE
NEW PATH TO THE RANKOT.

Śrīmat Sāhasa-mallaḥ Siṅhalapatih Kālingawaṅśāgrāṇir
Āgamyātra Kalingato 'rgghitavate Lankādhiraḥjyaṣṛiyām
Āyushmatpṛtanādhipāya mahatīm grāmādhikāṅ sampadam
Dattavān* kṛtavān svayaṅ kṛtavidām ekādhiraḥjye padam.

Śrī siri-sara Okāwas-parapurehi¹ mulu sakwala ek-sat-
kala² Kālinga cakrawartti paramparāyāta, Śrī Goparājayan
wahanse Bahidāloka mahādēwīn wahanse kusin Siṅhapurehi
prasūtawū,³ asama sāhasayen⁴ Sāhasa Malla yayi wirudu lada,
siri Saṅgabo Kālinga Wijaya-bāhu raja pā wahanse, palamu
Lankāyehi rajasiri⁵ pāmīna siṭi Niṣṣanka Malla nam bānan
wahanse swarggastha wū pasu; hiru astayāta⁶ giya tēna⁷

TRANSLATION.

[Sanskrit.] The illustrious Sāhasa Malla, King of Ceylon,
and chief of the Kālingan race, having come over here from
Kalinga, gave to the deserving and venerable aged chieftain
the great fortune of the Lordship of Ceylon, together with
much land, giving a share in his absolute power to those who
were grateful to him.

Come of the stock of the *Kālinga* Emperors, who, descended
from the sacred and illustrious race of *Ikshwāku*, brought the
whole earth under one umbrella, born at *Sinhapura*, in the
womb of *Bahidāloka* (the large-eyed one), the chief queen
of the illustrious *Goparāja*; the illustrious king Saṅgabo
Kālinga Wijaya Bāhu was, on account of his unequalled
daring, celebrated under the name of SĀHASA MALLA, "the
excellent by courage." After his elder brother, *Niṣṣanka*
Malla, who before him had come to the regal dignity in
Ceylon, had gone to heaven; when, like a number of stars

VARIOUS READINGS.

¹ A. sirisiramakāwas°, B. sirisiramakāwas°. ² A. eksakwalasatkōṭala. ³ A.
prasutawu. ⁴ A. asamasahayen, B. dasamasāhasayen. ⁵ B. rajasi. ⁶ A. B.
hastayāta. ⁷ B. tena.

* The second syllable should be long; the MS. reads dattovan or dantyan.

taru gananak se kīpa rājakenakun⁸ gili giya kalhi,⁹ Lan-
kāwa aswāmika wæ,¹⁰ sanda¹¹ udā no lat ræyak se anduruwa
tubu sanda ;¹² Lan-kādhikāra Lolupælā¹³ kulu dun næwi
ābonāwan,¹⁴ taman ṣrata ṣīla kulācārādi mantrī gunen yedī
nītiparama wana¹⁵ heyin tamanta parama mita wū Lan-kādhikā-
kāra Lolupælākulu¹⁶ budalnāwan hā ekwa, “rajahu¹⁷ næti
rājyaya¹⁸ nam niyamuwā næti næwak se no pawatneya,
hiru næti dawasa se no hoboneya, Buddha ṣāsanaya da anasak
nætiwa nirālabha¹⁹ wanneya, tawada Lakdiwa²⁰ Wijaya rāja-
yan Yakshapralaya koṭa kanu mul bā tænu wiyalak se
pawat kala heyin ema waṅṣayehi²¹ rajun bohose rakshākala²²
tænaya, e²³ bæwin mehi raja kala Niṣṣanka Malla swāminge
malanuwan wahanse Kalingu raṭa yawā waḍā-awut losasun

after the sun has set, several kings had sunk and gone, and Ceylon being without a ruler, was dark as a night without the rising of the moon, Lolupælākulu, Adhikār of the realm, and Lord High Admiral, spoke (as follows) with Lolupælākulu, Adhikār of the realm and Lord High Treasurer, who, —as he excelled in ethics, being endowed with all the qualities of an adviser, by his faithful disposition and family virtues,— had become his dearest friend.

“The kingdom without a king, like a ship without a steersman, will not continue; like a day without the sun, will not flourish; and the religion of Buddha, without regularity, will become profitless: and further, after Wijaya rāja drove away the devils, and made Ceylon like a field formed by the tearing out of stumps and roots, it is a place which has been much protected by kings of that family: therefore let us send to the country of Kalinga and fetch the younger brother of the Lord Niṣṣanka Malla who was reigning here, and thus secure the government of the world.” Having determined to do so, they sent to Kalinga the chief Malli-

⁸ A. B. kenakun. ⁹ A. tanhi. ¹⁰ A. wa. ¹¹ B. sana. ¹² A. awuruduwata-sata, B. anduruwatubusata. ¹³ B. pælæ. ¹⁴ A. duttæti abonāwan, B. dunnæwi abonāwan. ¹⁵ A. parawawana, B. parawacana. ¹⁶ A. kulū. ¹⁷ A. raja. ¹⁸ A. rājyayanama, B. rājyanama. ¹⁹ B. niralambha. ²⁰ B. Lakdiwanam. ²¹ B. wansayehi. ²² B. parikshākala. ²³ A. tawada e.

rakumha yi'' bænā niṣcaya koṭa, swāmi²⁴ paksha pāta dhīra sāra gunen yukta e raṭa wæsi Mallikārjjunā nam pradhāni Kalingu raṭa yawā, ārādhana koṭa, maha pelaharin genwā, Soli raṭin²⁵ Kahakoṇḍa-paṭṭana²⁶ mæ waḍā hinduwā, ratnā-bharaṇa wastrādīn matu wana rājya śrīyāṭa²⁷ anurūpa śrīn²⁸ satkāra karana kalhi, e bawa²⁹ asā anugraha³⁰ parigraha dekaṭa pohosat losasun raknā rājawarayan no kæmæti wa tama tamāge³¹ ma adhipatwaya patā wignā karana durmman-trīn de hawuruddakin³² sādha, pun sanda nagā pānā se subha nækat³³ mohot muhudu piṭa³⁴ maha potin³⁵ nirupadra wa koṭa waḍā awut, Tri-siṅhalaya ēkādhapatra³⁶ koṭa Buddha³⁷ warsha (1743) ek dahas hat siya te sālīs hawurudu tunmas sat wisi dawasak giya tena Binara pura doloswak lada Badā dā subha nækat mohotin abhiseka karawu me ananya-sādha-ṛaṇa-daskamāṭa taman wahanseṭa palamuwannehi senewi rat

karjjunā, who was a resident of that country, well affected towards his master, and of a brave and firm disposition, and having conciliated (the prince), and brought him with a great retinue from the *Soli* country, and placed him at the port of *Kahakoṇḍa*, they hospitably entertained him with all the splendour of jewels, ornaments, and robes suitable to the dignity of the kingship to be.

Whilst this was being done, some evil-designing men, each considering and hoping for his own advancement, did not desire kings who would secure the government of the world, (but) in two years, having overthrown them, raising and showing as it were the moon in its fullness, they brought him safely, at a lucky moment, over the sea in a great ship, and having united the three divisions of Ceylon under one sceptre, 1743 years 3 months and 27 days after the Nirvāṇa of Buddha, at the full moon of the month Binara, on Thursday, at a lucky moment, him they crowned. For this service, unequalled by others, in the first year of his reign he

²⁴ B. swāmī. ²⁵ B. raṭa. ²⁶ B. paṭṭamæ. ²⁷ B. rājjasrīyāṭa. ²⁸ B. śrī. ²⁹ A. mabawa, B. eba. ³⁰ A. anugraha. ³¹ B. tamange. ³² B. hawuruddaki. ³³ A. sahanækat, B. sāhanakat. ³⁴ A. B. muhunupita. ³⁵ A. mahapeta, B. mahapeti. ³⁶ A. ēkādapatra, B. ēkātapatra. ³⁷ B. Budha.

pata bandawā³⁸ agra mantrīkota siṭuwā, meweni daruwan³⁹ lada mawunṭa wædi⁴⁰ satkāra kalamanā wē dæyi mowun māniyanṭa Lankātilakadēwī yayi nam dī baḍaran pata bandawā boho sammāna dī hira sanda pamunu koṭa Lak-wijayasingu senewi ābonāwanṭa⁴¹ dī wadāla gamwara hā pariwāra hā⁴² siyalu sampattiyata, matu wana rajadaruwan udu taman⁴³ tamanṭa daskam kala un rakshā-kirīma rāja dharmma heyin, wilopayak no koṭa mema paridden tabā dī mawun waṅsha rakshā karanu mānawæyi silālekha karawā wadāla seka. Me balabalā rāja wallabha wa siṭi amāptytā-dihu da balātkārayen me kī deya gattu⁴⁴ nam wēwayi⁴⁵ rajasthaka kalāhu nam wēwayi⁴⁶ rājyaya mækuwā nam weti, kulen hīnayan hā da kawuḍu ballan⁴⁷ hā da samanam weti. Eheyin swāmi⁴⁸ pakshapāta wa rakshā karannā kæmættāwun-wisin⁴⁹ mowunṭa dun hæma sampat rakshā karanu mānawī.⁵⁰

gave to the honourable one the office of Commander-in-chief, and made him his Prime Minister: and thinking, "to the parents of such children much honour should be done," he gave their mother the name Lankātilakadēwī (the princess, the ornament of Ceylon), and girded her with a golden girdle, and gave her much honour.

And using (the royal sign manual of) sun and moon, he was pleased to make a record on stone that future princes might in a similar manner protect their family, and leave undisturbed the complete enjoyment of the lands and dignities he had been pleased to grant to the Commander-in-chief Lak-wijaya Singu; for it is the duty of kings to protect those who have done them service. If ministers and others who enjoy royal favour should, after seeing this (inscription), take by force the things here mentioned, or claim them as property of the crown, the kingdom will go to ruin, and they will become like low-caste men, and like dogs and crows. Therefore, let them protect the wealth granted to them by Him who desired to protect those who had been loyal.

³⁸ A. B. banawā. ³⁹ A. daru. ⁴⁰ A. B. wædi. ⁴¹ A. -sīngu-, B. -hingu-.
⁴² A. omits hā. ⁴³ A. tama. ⁴⁴ A. gattru, B. gathu. ⁴⁵ A. wæwayi. ⁴⁶ A. wewayi. ⁴⁷ B. ballā. ⁴⁸ A. swāmī. ⁴⁹ B. kæmætta. ⁵⁰ A. mānawī.

Devas Sāhasa-Malla esha jagatām mānyāṣayām yācatē
 Trāyan yad dr̥dhapakshapātadhuriṇām kshātro 'bhidharm-
 māparam
 Āyushmatpṛtanāpateḥ kṛtavatām Kālingavaṅṣodayām
 Candrākhyāvadhisampadām sahasato rakshantu vaṅṣyān
 nr̥pāḥ.

B.—THE RUWANWÆLI INSCRIPTION FOUND IN 1874 BY
 NĀRANWITA UNNĀNSE, AT THE S.E. ENTRANCE TO THE
 TERRACE ROUND THE RUWANWÆLI DĀGABA AT ANU-
 RĀDHAPURA.

- (1). Śrīmat-wū, tyāga - satya - śauryyādi - guṇa - gaṇayen
 asādhārana wū, Okā-was-raja-parapuren ā, Kālinga-
- (2). cakrawarrti-rāja-waṅṣayāta tilakāya-samāna wæ, Sinha-
 purayehi sajāta-wū, Niṣṣaṅka
- (3). Malla-Kālinga-Parākramabāhu-rajapā-wahansē ; swa-
 waṅṣayāta pa ramparāyāta
4. Lamkādwīpayehi ek se-sat koṭṭæ; mālu Parākrama-bāhu
 wahanse pūrwa-rāja-
5. carita ikmæ kala ati-dasa-awinayen pīḍita-wū dilindu-
 wæ gos sorakam koṭṭæ
6. jīwatwana boho janayā jīwitāsāhæræ sorakam karanne
 yan'
7. āsāwen wedæyi, ran-ridī-maṣuran-mutu-mænik-wastrā-
 bharaṇādi un-un-kæmati-wastu hā
8. sarak-gam-bim-ādī abhaya dī, sorakam harawā ; sesu
 boho janayā da ē ē dukkhayen galawā, mesē

TRANSLATION.

After Niṣṣanka Malla Kālinga Parākrama Bāhu, who was born at Sinhapura, as it were the crowning ornament of the imperial Kālingan race, the descendants of King Ikshvāku ; and who was unequalled in the number of his virtues, generosity, truth, heroism, and the like ; (4) had made one authority (supreme) in the island of Ceylon, which belonged to his family by ancestral right ; (8) he put down robbery by relieving, through gifts of cattle and fields, and of gold and silver coins,